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Evaluation of sustainability models

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1. Executive Summary

The scope of this deliverable is to evaluate the existing funding models and business models in the context of establishing the Genome EDIC.

This report relies almost entirely on the work previously done in the 2.1 report establishing a cost overview, the 2.2 report defining an initial cost contribution and central budget framework and the 2.6 report mapping existing funding and business models. As such this report is in particular an analysis of the findings presented in the 2.6 report, linking the legal, organizational and technical and governance attributes of the Genome-EDIC with the funding mechanisms in existence, and discussing the match between funding mechanisms/sources and the vision of the 1+MG.

The starting point for that discussion is to focus on funding for database infrastructure and funding for computing infrastructure, considering that these are the key components of the Genome-EDIC which incur significant costs, and because it is critical to develop a long term funding model, in which those two critical components can be addressed within the same overall organizational framework.

The key conclusions from this report are:

- There is no clear long term funding mechanism for database infrastructure, apart from depending on membership fees and short term project funding. A key challenge is the cumulative nature of building database infrastructure. Existing database infrastructures within research depend heavily on strong community engagement in order to bridge funding cycles.
- There are to some extent more easy avenues to fund computer infrastructure - in part because of the fit between the short time funding cycles and the life cycle of computers. A key challenge is the match between the requirements of a life science compute resource and the usability of a generic compute resource towards those aims. Past experience suggests that life science computer systems are often operated independently of other HPC resources - because of the nature of the computer needs, and the need for long term planning and capacity building.
- There are strong indications from the analysis, that there are key parameters that need to be addressed, in order to ensure enough agility for long term sustainability and for a business model to work for the EDIC:
 - National governance: A strong link to national stakeholders - ensuring buy-in and flexibility towards leveraging investments in the life science and health care domain and in order to create avenues for sourcing both genomic and clinical data from the clinical domain and to engage into EHDS. .
 - Technical interoperability between software components (composability) to ensure that the platform is agile, and can be changed over time in accordance with new or added requirements and needs, allowing for national flexibility in implementation and to ensure that there are clear separations of concerns and a clear division of roles - to ensure that there is a clear demarcation between what the core infrastructure does, and what it enables others to do with that resource.

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

	Contributed
<p>Outcome 1</p> <p>Secure federated infrastructure and data governance needed to enable sustainable and secure cross border linkage of genomic data sets in compliance with the relevant and agreed legal, ethical, quality and interoperability requirements and standards based on the progress achieved by the 1+MG initiative.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 2</p> <p>Platform performing distributed analysis of genetic/genomic data and any linked clinical/phenotypic information; it should be based on the principle of federated access to data sources, include a federated/multi party authorisation and authentication system, and enable application of appropriate secure multi-party and/or high-end computing, AI and simulation techniques and resources.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 3</p> <p>Clear description of the roles and responsibilities related to personal data and privacy protection, for humans and computers, applicable during project lifetime and after its finalisation.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 4</p> <p>Business model including an uptake strategy explaining the motivation, patient incentives and conditions for all stakeholders at the different levels (national, European, global) to support the GDI towards its sustainability, including data controllers, patients, citizens, data users, service providers (e.g., IT and biotech companies), healthcare systems and public authorities at large.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 5</p>	Yes

Sustained coordination mechanism for the GDI and for the GoE multi-country project launched in the context of the 1+MG initiative.	
<p>Outcome 6</p> <p>Communication strategy – to be designed and implemented at the European and national levels.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 7</p> <p>Capacity building measures necessary to ensure the establishment, sustainable operation, and successful uptake of the infrastructure.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 8</p> <p>Financial support to the relevant stakeholders to enable extension, upgrade, creation and/or physical connection of further data sources beyond the project consortium or to implement the communication strategy and for capacity-building.</p>	Yes

3. Methods

This report discusses the opportunities and potential of different funding sources - and how those could fit into the 1+MG framework. The report also identifies the gaps in the existing funding sources and funding mechanisms towards the aims of the 1+MG vision, and discusses key parameters and issues to be investigated building the long term sustainability framework and the business and funding models.

Whereas the 2.6 report "Mapping of existing funding and business models" gives a general overview of funding sources and business mechanisms, the actual implementation of different funding and business models have not been fully investigated - In part because many of the existing infrastructures do not apply a business model framework to their funding scheme. Many base the revenue on country membership fees, project funding and in-kind contribution, in a more or less tacit funding model - including the occasional PPP and innovation track - which is still heavily based on public research. Most European scale infrastructures do not cover research in combination with other use cases like envisioned for the Genome EDIC - it is this combination of different uses that requires us to consider other funding streams - and short term funding.

4. Description of work accomplished

This report aims at evaluating possible sustainability models as learnt from other research infrastructures and the evaluation of options. This is not a comprehensible analysis of the long term sustainability for the EDIC - based on the previous reports the evaluation is going to focus on two critical cost areas for the Genome EDIC that collectively represent separate and critical layers in the overall infrastructure: Database and HPC infrastructure. These areas are by far the most critical ones to address in terms of long term sustainability of the Genome-EDIC.

Continuing from the 2.1 report apart from cost areas there should also be some reflections on the distribution of cost types, based on the Roos/Hooft typology¹

1. **Development of Services:** Any activity that can change what is exactly offered to users. Typically project based funding coupled with in-kind contribution (hours).
2. **Operational Costs:** Any activity that is needed to offer the services to external customers. Capital investment and operational staff - sensitive to level of activity.

¹ Manuscript in preparation,

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Ng0G7XnMQwjY1Kax5fgKow4aME-SUUeRWEFqhMLR5LI/edit?usp=sharing>

3. **Organisational Costs:** Any activity to maintain an organisation that runs service development and operations. Long term operational budget. Some sensitivity to activity.

4.1 Current funding for database infrastructure for research purposes

In learning from other sustainability models from other research infrastructures, one must be very careful in understanding also what the differences are, since those differences can have a big impact on the costs and business model. This is particularly true on the data side of the Genome EDIC.

In research a data repository is a centralised or virtual/distributed data space in which scientists can deposit the data associated with their research, which many funders today require in order to preserve the data with persistent identifiers and thus facilitate discovery and reuse of the data. In most cases a repository works on the premise that it is the researcher that is the data controller, and the repository that is the processor of data. EGA² is such a data repository that operates as a deposition database. Researchers upload their data as-is and users search the data catalogue for datasets, apply for access and download them. The federated EGA works on the same model, except the data is accessible not through a central database, but through database infrastructure provided by (national) nodes.

On the other end of the spectrum of data-providing services is the concept of a Knowledge Base (Gabella et al, 2018). Knowledge Bases are dynamic data collections built from multiple sources which are not archived as-is, but also reviewed, distilled and annotated, concentrating high quality knowledge collected from different sources. UniProt³ is an example of a knowledge base, accumulating and condensing high quality protein sequencing and annotation information.

There is a substantial difference between the operation of a repository and a knowledge base. Both are important and both support the uptake of the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and reusable) allowing for more transparent and fast reuse of data. Within this, repositories concentrate efforts mainly on making data findable and accessible, relying on the users to deposit data and adding limited quality control and standardisation; Deposition databases serve as experts in data preservation, taking this responsibility out of the hands of individual researchers and satisfying the basic needs for reproducibility of science and reusability of data that society now requires.

Many research funders require researchers to have a data management plan in place included in their funding application, expressing how the data is going to be kept adhering to the FAIR principles. Some funders also provide the funding to realize those plans. Repositories are there to support researchers with functional and community-driven solutions for long term storage

² EGA European Genome-Phenome Archive: <https://ega-archive.org/>

³ UniProt: <https://www.uniprot.org/>

Knowledge bases focus on making the collected data interoperable and thereby make it reusable as a single combined data set (ideally) - for this reason the information is required to be quality controlled and harmonized in order to:

- improve the searchability of the data
- accumulate critical mass for more diverse statistical analysis
- efficiently process the data using advanced algorithms on high performance computer systems.

In the real world there is no black and white distinction between a repository and a knowledge-base; there are many intermediate forms.

The 1+MG initiative aims to set up an infrastructure in Genome EDIC that is as close as possible to a knowledge base. Post-curation of data is expensive - the more the researchers plan and adhere to agreed data standards, the easier the transition into the knowledge base is. And vice versa - if a researcher uses a knowledge base dataset for the research rather than collect data independently, there is really no need to store another copy of the data - only the results and documentation for how those results were derived from the data - making huge savings in the overall storage need.

There are no easy or directly applicable funding sources for database infrastructure. This was confirmed in the 2.6 report mapping out potential funding sources. This problem has been identified and discussed for many years, both in the context of the life sciences and within EOSC (EOSC AISBL, 2022, Gabella et al 2017, ELIXIR 2023). Research funders are rarely willing to commit long term to the operation of database infrastructure, committing in most cases only 4-5 year funding cycles, which is the funding horizon that research funders typically operate under. The most stable funding mechanisms are through those research funding schemes in which costs for long term data management are eligible for funding, but there is no guarantee that those funds are channelled into community-maintained repositories! In many cases researchers will opt for the simplest and cheapest solution which is often to store the data on their own servers or in a university's generic database infrastructure which satisfies the basic requirements for reproducibility but hardly serves findability/searchability and re-use for secondary purposes. This fragmentation of data into hard-to-reach places is an unfortunate structural effect of creating funding mechanisms for long term data management that focus on deposition - that PI's and universities may be inclined to use their own bespoke deposition solution, limiting the ability to build knowledge bases across institutions and countries.

The fact that some community-driven databases have managed to thrive and grow for a longer period than 4-5 years is not based on a clear funding regime, but on strong institutions with clear governance behind those initiatives (e.g. Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics for UNIPROT and ELIXIR for others) on a very strong commitment and support within a tight research community, dedicated to channelling resources into the database infrastructure - either because there is a shared research mission or there is a win/win in accumulating data from different sources for similar purposes.:

- Dedication from users to upload research data according to community standards,

- Financial support towards the core data resources in return for making data freely accessible
- Coordination of fundraising, service, and data quality activities towards those aims.

ELIXIR is the institutionalization of that sustainability model for life science research data infrastructure and has been very successful at that for a number of years, depending not on a long term funding commitment, but rather being in a position to capitalize on a continued stream of short term project funding, a strong community dedication and solutions for donating data and a relatively small national membership contribution through an agreement with member states.

4.1.2: Evaluation of current models of funding of database infrastructure for research

Where do the current sustainability models NOT fit the Genome-EDIC?

- Community building is a critical component of the current sustainability model for databases, but requires an agreement between infrastructure and research (community) priorities. Since the EDIC will have to cater to a large contingent of users and user communities and since it will operate on data derived from health care it will be challenging to accommodate that within existing structures and community engagement in infrastructure provisioning
- The current models based on community interaction and commitment puts the burden of establishing data documentation and quality requirements on the data providers, which makes it very hard to put a charge on accessing the data. Asking someone (with limited funding) to make an effort on the data included for the good of the community, cannot work together with a model in which the very same data donors also pay for access to the data
- The services may be difficult to expand outside the original community. Building a community for a data infrastructure requires that the providers of the data are also the ones most directly benefiting from the infrastructure. If that link is not present - it will be hard to argue that the data providers should volunteer to donate data - particularly into a high quality knowledge base.
- Decisions are consensus-driven which may not allow for prioritisation or changing directions and dynamics
- There are likely many hidden or underreported costs/value adding activities that form part of the functioning of a community driven database infrastructure - a community and/or goal oriented focus on long term research goals and short term funding priorities.
- Infrastructure expectations from users and data holders can place opposing demands on the security measures: Managing the risks of data re-use to levels acceptable to the data holders can become or appear insurmountable for the re-users of the data.

Where does the Genome-EDIC not fit the current sustainability models?

- Under the data governance model foreseen for the Genome EDIC there is a need to establish a clear data controllership, which is very different from operating an infrastructure as a data processor on behalf of a researcher. It creates legal liabilities towards data access, and all processes to provide data towards end users must be well documented and risk-managed. Since the EDIC must also operate on clinically derived data, it requires decisions from health

care actors (who are inherently very risk averse when it comes to data sharing) in order to include data into the infrastructure - which requires that the infrastructure can **formally** demonstrate an extremely high level of adherence to data protection and risk management. (The **informal** or tacit awareness of data protection and risk management requirements within a research community may be an efficient way of managing data protection - however it is unlikely to convince health care data providers).

- The EDIC must orchestrate the secure processing environments in which the data is exposed to the users - Most database infrastructures, including EGA, UNIPROT and NIH allow the user to download the data from the database to an HPC system outside the control of the database infrastructure. This is a fundamental difference: taking operational responsibility for the data processing adds many layers of complexity in terms of service provision, cost recovery and risk management.
- The EDIC cannot depend on community engagement to ensure data inclusion from health care. The disengagement of research data users and research data contributors breaks the social contract that a community driven database rests on.
- The EDIC must cater to a very large pool of users across health care and Life science and medicine and bioinformatics. Any priority of resources towards one end, is likely to be at the cost of someone else. This is likely inherent to multipurpose infrastructure. The operation therefore requires a very high degree of transparency on who benefits, how the decisions are made, and what the funding sources are - it also requires good governance to manage the platform as a generic service, not ending up only supporting specific research missions. .
- The users of the output of the infrastructure are not necessarily engaged in building the infrastructure or provide data for the infrastructure. In addition to the points made above, it may very well lead to a customer/transactional approach rather than a partner/relational approach - not being aware or appreciative of the challenges to get services to market, and a distrust/lack of confidence in depending on the platform.
- The Genome EDIC is likely to require full transparency of the total-cost-of-ownership, which will make the infrastructure appear more expensive than database and compute infrastructure which operates partly based on community capacity on the input and output side (e.g. by diverting research project funding into the operation of research infrastructure) that risks underreporting the real cost and resource burn.
- The sheer scale of a database table that includes and maintains more than a million human whole genomes is complex and expensive in terms of manpower and storage requirements - and it may for that reason be difficult to accommodate within traditional funding mechanisms.

4.2 Current funding models for compute infrastructure

Since many of the fundamental differences between current funding models for database infrastructure and the complexity of the EDIC also apply to computer infrastructure there is no point in repeating these here.

In general at university, national and European level it seems that there is a higher degree of awareness and willingness to fund compute infrastructure for scientific purposes, than to fund long term database infrastructure - Computers have very short shelf lives of 4-6 years - For funders that means that the investment in HPC infrastructure fits much more easily into the funding cycles in research. It gives funders a "natural" ability to fund - and write of that investment without a long term commitment. Funders may also be more intrinsically attracted to sponsoring a new state of the art piece of technology, cutting ribbons and getting positive publicity, than to sponsoring the continued operation of a database. Presumably there is a political willingness and a strong narrative to invest into a resource that is an indispensable part of data-driven science.

For database infrastructure this is a lot harder. Funders understand that sponsoring a database infrastructure will be a commitment that has a longer funding perspective, than the usual funding cycles in research.

The EuroHPC Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC JU⁴) is a good example of a joint effort across Europe and private and public stakeholders to have a dedicated funding framework that allows Europe to operate computer infrastructure that is comparable to the capacity found in the rest of the world - predominantly in the US.

Bridging the need for continued computer upgrades and to avoid too many stop-gap cycles is at its crux the reason why EuroHPC was established - to alleviate and stabilize the funding model for a competitive resource that is continuously developing technologically.

However, whereas storage and thus database infrastructure has an accumulative cost profile, there are different dynamics in play when it comes to computational resources.

There is also a strong competitive edge narrative in computer investments. To have a cost-effective and competitive/functional HPC system in place, major upgrades are required every 4-6 years - in part because a new system will always have much higher capacity than a 5 year old system for the same depreciation cost and because scientific edge cases are likely to max out the capacity of the system in place - requiring continuous updates to stay scientifically relevant.

Simply put - Computer infrastructure has a broad support/appeal and a very tangible reward both for funders and research communities, whereas database infrastructure is an inherently long term commitment, accumulative in nature and much more specific to different communities - creating much less newsworthiness and collective support.

Where does the current sustainability model for computing NOT fit the Genome-EDIC?

Using the EuroHPC as an example, there are some generalizable problems at play with a model in which the Genome-EDIC depends on generic HPC systems. In principle EuroHPC has in its mission an obligation also to support life sciences, but it is a challenge to apply that mission statement to human genomics.

⁴ https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/about_en

Fundamentally the federated/distributed approach to data use governance does not fit the EuroHPC centralized operational and funding/governance model. EuroHPC operates a tiered system in which there are very few (nine) Tier 0 computers in Europe - catering to the absolute top compute needs. Then there are Tier 1, 2 and Tier 3, which are the local/national/cross country compute infrastructures, funded directly by national sources. It is not impossible to co-create the Genome-EDIC infrastructure in collaboration with EuroHPC JU - however it will depend massively on the governance and funding-willingness at national and local level to support that mission short and long term, since most of the funding will have to come from the national level directly.

Life science computer infrastructure for human health needs consistency and long term planning - it needs dedicated staff to run a complicated life science platform, tools, interfaces and data in/out protocols, it needs sufficient storage and scalability and for operating on special category human data it needs tight user management and regulatory compliance in place to operate - and for these reasons Life Science needs planning consistency over time - all things that are hard to put into a generic serve-all computer infrastructure depending on short term funding cycles and the priorities and decisions of others. This is the main reason that life science compute infrastructure for human health is frequently operated separately from other research areas that mainly require (similar) processing capacity across different scientific fields.

The nature of genomic and bioinformatic computer usage is a challenge to cater to in a generic application based HPC environment. High Performance Computing focuses on solving a single problem as quickly as possible, often involving complex simulations or calculations. The key is how many operations can be performed in a second (FLOPS) . High Throughput Computing (HTC) (which is the way most bioinformatic analysis works), on the other hand, is designed to handle many smaller tasks over a long period, prioritizing the completion of a large number of jobs in days, weeks, months or years, rather than the speed of individual tasks. What this means is that for bioinformatic analysis, designing an effective workflow in which data is moved from storage to compute and then out again is much more important than being able to calculate on a singular but very large calculation. (The analogy is, that you can tune a car engine for maximum speed OR long range - but not at the same time)

In many cases this also means that most users will have to be on the system for a considerable amount of time - in many cases continuously - which will inadvertently block other users from utilizing that part of the resource, creating frictions between communities needing ALL the compute power at once, vs those that need portions of it for extended periods of time.

The Genome-EDIC serves both health care and research, and is unlikely to be able to gain the support of research funders - at least without having a very clear understanding of the allocation mechanisms and funding streams across different ministries.

To sum up - It is not likely that the Genome-EDIC can capitalize directly or short term on the current sustainability model for HPC in Europe, implemented through EuroHPC JU. In part this is because the way the systems are built and how resources are allocated does not fit the operational model of a Life Science computer infrastructure. However, there is an opportunity to engage with actors on a

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national level to establish Tier 1-3 systems that can cater to life science and genomics specifically - the funding still needs to come from national sources, but the systems could form part of the national contribution towards the EuroHPC commitment. Basically, there is an opportunity to build national Life Science infrastructure within the scope of the investment pledge towards EuroHPC that anyway needs to be made. That will need to be investigated further - particularly if the resource allocation mechanism and the federated cross-border nature of the Genome-EDIC can be catered to under this model.

Having a coherent long term funding mechanism for life science compute infrastructure at national level feeding into the EuroHPC ecosystem is also an opportunity to build capacities within genomics, ensuring a more stable structure and career paths for critical technical staff and thus better opportunities to recruit and retain those people - something that is often difficult within digital research. Database managers, Systems architects, Compute scientists, systems administrators etc. are highly sought after people.

Further down the road it MAY be possible to capitalize on the EuroHPC Tier 0 systems for extreme high-end cases within Genomics - for instance for training AI models. But this requires a thorough data protection impact assessment (DPIA). Note also that moving data to a compute environment different from where it is kept and maintained is subject to agreement and conditions from the data provider in the Genome EDIC, and supporting such use cases is currently not on the priority list of the initiative. .

5. Discussion

(For a more detailed discussion please consult the discussion paper presented to the GOV partners in November 2024 (Rasmussen, 2024))

It has been evident all along, that existing funding sources and funding dynamics will not easily translate into the Genome-EDIC. However, at the same time Genome-EDIC is in as unique position at a national and European level, that it is an infrastructure that bridges stakeholders across health care, life science research and innovation, and due to the generic nature and scalability of the technical platform it has an enormous potential to be applied to many different needs across this ecosystem, in terms of providing flexible processing capacity and storage, and as a federated secure research platform.

But the key to unlocking that potential and channel new investments and existing funding streams into the EDIC and to avoid parallel structures and parallel investments is

- to build an **open and dynamic national partnership** between the different stakeholders to ensure the best possible governance and stakeholder engagement for the platform to develop and expand in a manner that is conducive for realising the potential it indeed has - to build a national life science research platform feeding into EHDS and European research initiatives.

- **The existing funding sources lack flexibility, scalability and also depend heavily on very rigid and singular funding sources**, making them vulnerable to shortsightedness without avenues to build long term sustainability. What is evident from the existing business/funding model for infrastructures is that they are built with a very clear definition of roles, services, targeted users and with a singular governance model - by design they are built to fit within narrow parameters - but this author also suspects that this is also why there are many parallel investments, that could have been more effectively run collectively - if there is a strong governance and a more clear mandate to separate infrastructure provision from end users and their research communities.
- There is a **need to ensure agility and co-ownership at both national and EU level**. While not impeding on the progression of genomics, the storage and compute platform that is needed for Genome EDIC functions can accommodate a host of applications and user communities across the ecosystem. Using this synergy will increase the fault tolerance tremendously and build constructive engagement that could ideally foster a continuous accumulation of support and thus funding for the long term sustainability of the platform. It will also allow mechanisms to source data from different stakeholders - which is certainly in the self-interest of the genomics community - fostering precision medicine requires collaboration across many different fields of science, in which genomics is only one modality.
- **Improving health care productivity and quality on one side and an excellence driven focus on generating new knowledge on the other side are extremely difficult to align**, and if this dichotomy is not carefully handled it will lead to an unproductive win/lose fight over priorities - and will not fulfil the vision of 1+MG. While the improvement of human health is the overarching goal for all stakeholders - this is approached very differently and with very different timescales within health care and research, Researchers will always be drawn towards infrastructure that can deliver peak performance and complex workloads catering to leading scientific use cases, with the purpose of expanding the horizon of human knowledge. This is an inherent function of research and a competitive research funding system that focuses on excellence and rewards initiative, with limited funding available. Health care on the other hand is liable towards patient care and its costs are under massive public scrutiny, and is required to implement new tools and workflows in highly complex systems focusing on documentation, cost-efficiency and consistency.
- There is a need to establish **a clear separation of what the infrastructure does and what it enables others to do with that resource**. This presents a challenge in building trust and constructive engagement - rather than constraining dependencies - which is very likely to lead to the separation of investments and parallel structures. Instead of coming up with a radically new model for funding, coordination and prioritisation, that is unlikely to work within two so fundamentally different approaches - the solution may be to build a framework that can work with both those approaches without accumulating dependencies but concentrate on the core functionalities that must be in place to allow different funding mechanisms, timescales and momentums to work downstream.

- It is also vital that the **technical implementation is done with composability of functionalities in mind**, ensuring that different service modules can be changed, improved and mixed in different configurations to allow flexibility and adaptation on the user side: that health care, research, industry and innovation agents can use the infrastructure as a base for their specific applications. For this reason what should be investigated for the long term sustainability and the business plan is to have a layered infrastructure approach separating functionalities, funding streams and governance into clearly demarcated areas

The goal at national and EDIC level should be to create a governance framework that **limits dependencies**, ensures enough agility to **allow for independence** and to **build mechanisms for interdependent activities** rather than get everybody to agree on the direction, under the assumption that eventually everything will be aligned. Failing to achieve this carries a huge risk of not achieving the EDIC's mission, mispending of valuable resources, loss of momentum and/or alienating funders and other stakeholders.

6. Conclusions & Impact

The main conclusion to be drawn from this report is that in order to build a business plan and long term sustainability it is vital to ensure that the 1+MG infrastructure is designed for the future, ensuring that it can cater to many users and stakeholders in a complicated funding landscape and with many parallel activities going on in the overall life science and health care eco system. For this reason technical Interoperability and governance responsiveness are key design parameters, which requires proper engagement at national level as well as European level and a careful approach towards implementation to ensure that it can fulfil the promise and potential it has across a wide array of applications - not being locked to a singular solution for everybody and implemented through a narrow scope of reference.

In any engineering project, at some point there is a need for an acceptance test - which is the last test before making the system available for actual use. Acceptance test evaluates if a product aligns with user needs and business requirements (which also includes regulatory and governance/stakeholder requirements). While the GDI project is not at this stage ready to run an acceptance test, work should begin on defining the acceptance criteria in accordance with criteria that match the needs required for the long term sustainability of the infrastructure - some of which will have to be derived from the data use governance framework, from the data protection and risk management framework - but also from the more generic principles discussed in chapter 5 of this report and the discussion paper presented to the GOV group in November 2024: A layered infrastructure approach, composability, avoidance of dependencies, a clear separation of roles and responsibilities, agility and integrity.

Key to any development of a business plan is to understand the nature of the product and the principles it works on to create targeted value to end users and sponsors. An exercise in how to do that will likely create a more coherent and universal mindset and language for how the many stakeholders involved in the GDI project can work together to fulfil the 1+MG vision.

7. Next steps

Based on the findings of this and the preceding three reports in the task towards a long term sustainability plan and business model framework, the next order of business is to develop the actual financial and business model framework for the 1+MG infrastructure.

Three subtasks in that are critical:

- Narrow down and specify as much as possible the requirements for national operations in terms of number FTEs, storage and computational resources. The challenge here is to develop a transparent investment plan over time, that takes into account also the dependency on the user interests and the available data sources.
- Develop and significantly expand the value propositions from the current state. The value propositions that are currently being discussed and operationalised through the GDI project are primarily focused on research edge cases. There is a strong need not to showcase the leading edge, but to present *low hanging fruit*: tangible value propositions for integration with EHDS, with other European life science initiatives and national personalised medicine initiatives. Without those value propositions, it will be hard to get enough buy-in from key stakeholders to realise the broad vision of the 1+MG framework.
- Put in place a consistent roadmap for implementation of the business model, including funding streams and cost recovery mechanisms, adapting the broad concepts of value proposition and business model canvas into a tangible action plan.

Continued exploration of funding sources and business models that could inspire and guide the implementation must also be followed.

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